

UNIVERSITY EDUCATION IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: *The use of educational platforms in education is not a novelty, but its increased importance is manifest since the pandemic outbreak. The faculties have very swiftly improved and introduced new modes of work that support distance learning. This paper addresses the current topics of education in digital environment. Along with an overview of educational platforms and tools used at Belgrade faculties during the 2020/2021 academic year, the benefits and drawbacks of online education are underscored. In order to obtain the answers as to how much the education in digital environment has managed to meet the expectations and requirements, the standpoints of professors and students have been analyzed. The results confirm that the form of education impacts the content and methodology which implies a new paradigm of education.*

Keywords: *educational platforms, digital environment, online education, university education, pandemic*

1. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Throughout the history, humans have been trying, by using machines, to make their labor easier and to improve all fields of work. In the history of education, the use of technology is nothing new. Online learning in its contemporary sense dates back to the second half of the 20th century. PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automated Teaching Operations) is considered a forerunner of this type of sharing knowledge, developed in 1960 at the University of Illinois, that enabled students to learn with the aid of interconnected computer terminals [1]. It was followed by the first individual online courses (the first online educational programme was launched in 1981 in the School of Management and Strategic Studies at the Western Behavioral Sciences Institute in La Jolla, California, the first fully online course was implemented in 1984 at the University of Toronto). The development of information and communication technology is accompanied with a growing number of universities and associated faculties that implement the modern technology in educational process to certain extent. MIT launched the Athena project in the 1980s that represented an experimental research on the use of computers in education [2]. In early 1990s, the Open University in Britain was one of the first to commence online learning courses, even though it started “testing of videotex (videotex) system OPTTEL, on a DEC-20 mainframe” [3] ten years earlier. It is presently among the top-rated distance learning universities, and it proudly states on its website: “The Open University is the UK’s largest academic institution and a world pioneer in distance learning. To date, we’ve taught more than two million students worldwide” [4]. How seriously and timely

they realized the importance of investing in this type of education is testified by the fact that in 2005 they were prepared to allocate GBP 5 million for improving the educational application Moodle (Modular Object Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment), to become later available to all members and users of the Moodle platform free of charge. Practical and concrete examples are accompanied with the works of theoreticians published in professional magazines. The introductory note of the magazine *American Journal of Distance Education* No. 1 of 1987 reveals that distance learning is not a novelty and that it is gaining momentum [5]. The magazine was launched ten years after the British Open University was already in operation and magazines with similar topics had been already published in Australia [6] and Canada [7]. A major breakthrough was made by Google in 2014 by launching its Google Classroom, which has seen its full-blown practical use during the pandemic.

When our country is concerned, it is noteworthy to mention the endeavors on setting up the Academic Computer Network (AMRES), which started developing in the first half of the 1990s, yet a significant progress could be noted only in early 2000s. In the second half of the 2000s, the Moodle platform started being used at the faculties of the Belgrade University, initially followed by an organized training course within the Computer Centre of the Belgrade University (RCUB). Today, according to the data available on its official website, Moodle has 280,000,000 registered users from 246 countries and 37,000,000 courses [8]. As an instance of good practice in preparation and implementation of online education, Metropolitan University was one of the first to introduce

complete online master studies. This experience helped its becoming the first to move to online education in March 2020, within merely 24 hours (when the state of emergency was pronounced in Serbia due to the pandemic) [9].

The development of technology is followed by the appearance of new modes of learning. One of innovative approaches is personalized e-Learning which, notwithstanding the challenges, brings more efficient learning and satisfied participants in educational process [10].

2. RESEARCH ON EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND LEARNING IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

As of the corona pandemic outbreak in 2020, the use of various learning platforms for educational purposes inevitably increased. A growth in the number of papers and research covering this topic is evident. Some of them offer a broad view of students' (dis)satisfaction with distance learning [11], [12] and show how teachers adapted during online education [13]. Some texts are dedicated to specific platforms, such as Hangouts Meet, Zoom and Microsoft Teams [14] or they address the use of educational tools for successful acquisition of curriculum in specific subjects, such as the application of Moodle in learning foreign languages [15].

Aspiring to make a comprehensive overview of the application of educational platforms on the university level, to disclose facts, perceptions, views and statements of respondents regarding the educational platforms that support online learning, two anonymous surveys have been created – for teachers and for students separately. The survey was made by using google forms (for employees: forms.gle/1JV4TEZmhGh6Ce229 and for students: forms.gle/uwUXgrcB9SiFsEmc6) distributed by email at the end of second semester of the 2020/2021 academic year. What makes this survey specific are the respondents themselves. Namely, professors and students from state faculties within the Belgrade University took part in the survey (the Faculty of Philology, the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, the Faculty of Teachers Training, the Faculty of Economy, the Faculty of Physics and the Faculty of Geography) and from private universities – Metropolitan University (the Faculty of Management) and UNION - Nikola Tesla (the Faculty of Diplomacy and Security, the Faculty of Sports). Starting hypotheses: (a) respondents have used educational platforms, (b) they are positively inclined towards their application, (c) the use of new technologies changes the form and content of work and (d) in the future, respondents desire the education that at least partly supports distance learning.

Results and Discussion

In the study 123 respondents took part (48 professors and 75 students). Since five employees and three students

have not used educational platforms in the observed period, the answers of 115 respondents have been analyzed. As the reasons why the employees have not used platforms (one full professor, two associate professors, one assistant professor and one teaching assistant) it was stated that they preferred conventional teaching, teaching smaller groups which enables traditional education, or that online courses were not convenient due to the type of curriculum. Students (one student of the first year, one student from the fourth year and one master student) mostly had practical reasons – due to work, difficulties in balancing real-time lectures and professional/private obligations, but they also said that such method of teaching was not convenient and that they experienced a lack of motivation.

We appreciate the time and efforts of the respondents who contributed to the achievement of the study goals.

The survey was compiled from a combination of questions – open and closed types, multiple choice options, while the Likert-type scale was applied for scaling responses. The answers to the identical questions for both groups, comprising a major part of the survey, were compared. In the first part, personal data were collected – years of age, vocation, or the year of study (graphs 1 and 2).

Graph 1: Structure of respondents by academic achievements

Graph 2: Structure of respondents by the year of study

The second, major part of the survey referred to the used platforms, the reasons for their use, benefits and drawbacks... Most of the employees, 26 of them (60.5%)

has used educational platforms even before the pandemic, whereas 17 (39.5%) have first encounters with the platforms during the transition to online education. UNICEF has provided a proposal of educational digital tools, including a brief description, for interactive education and online learning, online resources for coding and developing and educational video channels [16]. Some of them have been applied in our educational system. If we compare the answers, we can deduce that both groups of respondents most frequently use Zoom (67 respondents) and Moodle (37 respondents), followed by Skype (23), Microsoft Teams (17), Google meet (15), Edmodo (6), Google Classroom (6), BigBlueButton (4), BigMarker (2), LAMS (Learning Activity Management System – 3 respondents) and Jamboard, Webex, Voov and Viber one respondent each. The teaching staff mainly opted for the platforms recommended by the faculty, i.e. the faculty itself holds software and licenses. Most of the students opted for Zoom due to its ease of use. This platform has been mostly used for lectures in real time, whereas Moodle had more of a passive role, since it was predominantly used for uploading data and educational

were also faculty websites, professor’s websites and social networks. It is evident that the students of private faculties used Skype and Google Meet more often, while the Belgrade University, besides Zoom, used also Moodle to large extent. Moodle is an *open source* software which is why it was widely used before the pandemic, too. Many faculties integrated Zoom in order to be able to facilitate online lectures within Moodle, which is why these two platforms are often stated together in the answers provided.

The answers (multiple choice) about the reasons for using educational platforms overlap within both groups of respondents (Graph 3). They are mostly used for online lectures, followed by using/setting up learning material and video recordings of lectures, and they are least used for knowledge assessments and online tests. Even though online education was mostly implemented in real time, most of the students (63.4%) prefers to playback the recorded material later at the time that suits them best.

material. Important sources of information for students
Graph 3: Reasons for using educational platforms

This type of work called for certain changes and adjustments. Teaching staff stated (multiple choice was provided as an option) that they had to adjust the method of work (75%), to conform the content of lectures to the new type of teaching (27,5%), to stop keeping the attendance records (22.5%), to change the valuation of pre-exam obligations (17.5%), while one segment of respondents (17.5%) has not changed anything compared to traditional mode of education.

The question that referred to benefits and drawbacks was of an open type. Table 1 (Educational platforms and teaching) features the most common answers. Based on these answers, we can conclude that both groups of respondents perceive similar benefits and drawbacks. One the one side, there is mobility, the possibility to attend lectures from any place and to have a postponed access to material, but the major drawback is a lack of direct communication, motivation, establishing interpersonal relations and socialization.

Table 1: Educational platforms and teaching

	Advantages	Disadvantages	Evaluation of online education
Teaching staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher mobility - Higher attendance - Availability of material - Higher flexibility - Work from home, time saving in commuting to and from the faculty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of interaction, discussion and exchanging views - Lack of non-verbal communication - Technical prerequisites - Objective testing not viable - Lack of focus and motivation on students' part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fully satisfied (30.2%) - Partly satisfied (51.2%) - Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (14%) - Dissatisfied to large extent (4.6%) - Dissatisfied (0%)
Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to follow the courses from any place - Possibility of subsequent playback of classes and access to learning material - Time and money savings - Study and work - Convenience of studying at home 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet connectivity prerequisite - Lack of motivation - Lack of sense of studying - Lack of familiarity with professors and students - Too much screen time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fully satisfied (23.3%) - Partly satisfied (34.2%) - Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (27.4%) - Dissatisfied to large extent (11%) - Dissatisfied (4.1%)

Likert-type scale was used for assessing online education (1 – fully satisfied, 2 – partly satisfied, 3 – neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 4 – Dissatisfied to large extent and 5 – dissatisfied). The provided answers (as shown in Table 1) reveal that majority of respondents is partly or even fully satisfied with this type of work. However, what is surprising is that the percentage of satisfaction among students is lower, but it should be taken into account that this group of respondents is larger. Based on these results, the expected answers to the last question – How would you like education to unfold in the future (not only during pandemic)? The majority is for a so-called hybrid, or mixed model (teaching staff 70.8% and students 61.3%) – a combination of online and traditional education, while the exercises are to be preferably held in classrooms. Each of these models has its benefits and drawbacks, yet the best of each should be adopted, and many shortcomings can be overcome by using various digital tools [17]. Their application requires certain skills, computer, IT and digital literacy. Almost equal percentage is only for traditional type of education (27.1% professors and 28% students). Despite a noticeable disappointment with online education, more students (10.7%) support online education alone, as compared to employees (2.1%).

3. FINAL OBSERVATIONS

The development of information and communication technologies has affected all segments of work. The model of education departs from long-held, traditional frameworks. New technologies have seen the application in education even before the outbreak of the corona virus pandemic. The pandemic has only accelerated the

implementation of educational platforms and quickly showed all benefits and drawbacks of this type of work. In applying state-of-the-art technology, its opportunities and strengths should be considered. Education is *de facto* undergoing changes, but nothing can replace direct communication. That is why the initial expectations have been confirmed – an optimal mode of work is a combination of traditional and new in the future. Technological advance inevitably imposes modernization and reform of education. The research showed that e-Learning brings changes in the work, but the participants in the educational process have embraced novelties and assessed them positively to large extent. These and similar research should encourage consideration of a fundamental change in the concept of education, both regarding, both in terms of its form and its content and methodology.

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